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THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMMUNICATIVE-ACTIVITY MODEL OF CONTROL IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TESTING

Abstract

The article is devoted to the ways of implementation of the communicative-active model of control in foreign language testing. The essence, advantages and disadvantages of linguistic testing were analyzed. The implementation of the communicative-active model of control in testing English professional-oriented texts reading skills is considered.

Key words: *model of control, linguistic test, reading competence, psychological mechanism of reading.*

Problem statement. Ukraine's entry into the European Higher Education Area, due to the strengthening of international relations and the integration of European states, has led to radical changes in the field of education. The current state of development of the economy, science and technology requires higher educational institutions to train highly qualified specialists capable of effective foreign language communication, especially in situations of professional communication that may arise in the course of their future professional activities. All this requires the development of students' speech competence, and therefore the use of new approaches to the organization of the educational process and the process of controlling foreign language learning as an integral part of the latter.

An important prerequisite for effective foreign language learning is to ensure control over the level of formation of students' speech competence in various types of speech activity at all stages of the learning process. In non-linguistic universities, a special role is played by the formation and control of students' speech competence in reading professionally oriented foreign language texts, since the learning process is focused on the practical use of language for reading for professional purposes.

Literature review. According to the theory of activity, the main purpose of speech is to serve as a means of communication, which in turn performs the functions of communication as an exchange of ideas for the purpose of mutual understanding. This statement forms the basis of the communicative-activity model of control. Taking into account the available publications [1], this model can be considered generally accepted for teaching a foreign language (FL). Its popularity is due to the fact that the purpose of teaching FL should not be to accumulate theoretical knowledge, but to master the appropriate types of foreign language speech activity and to form such speech skills and abilities that are necessary for FL communication in the process of solving various practical (professionally oriented) tasks by modeling real communication situations.

Based on the Council of Europe's Pan-European Recommendations (PEG) [2] and the Standard English for Professional Communication (SEC) [3] and taking

into account the data of previous studies [4], the test method of control can be considered as one that corresponds to modern trends in the organization of the education system in general and the methodology of teaching English in particular.

In view of the above, it is necessary to analyze the ways of implementing the communicative activity model of control when testing reading skills in English professionally oriented texts.

The objective of the study. The organization of a reliable control system requires, first of all, an analysis of modern control models, in particular communicative and activity-based, and ways of its implementation in the formation of speech competence of future teacher-engineers in reading English-language professionally oriented texts.

The statement of the main material. Within the framework of the modern education system, testing is of great importance, since tests are a convenient and economical form of control. Systematic testing stimulates the activity and attention of students in classes, increases their responsibility in completing educational tasks. Testing as a component of the control system should be based on a certain control model. In the methodology, the term "model" means the implementation of the leading idea of learning in practice, or, in other words, a learning strategy. At the present stage, the most commonly used control models are systemic, communicative-activity, competency-based, and level-based.

In the practice of domestic control, tests were introduced into the educational process in the 1920s after the abolition of the point system of assessment, in the early 1960s with the advent of programmed learning. In 1992-1993, testing of graduating students and applicants was introduced. In our time, a system of independent external testing is being implemented.

Testing as a term means the use and conduct of a test, as well as a set of stages of planning, development and approval of tests, as well as processing and interpretation of their results. Linguistic and didactic testing deals with the development and use of language and speech tests, and linguistic and didactic tests are aimed at checking the level of language (linguistic) and

speech (communicative) competence of persons undergoing testing.

Let us consider the structure of linguistic and didactic tests.

Tests with 40-50 tasks form complex tests, the components of which are test parts (for testing global elements of speech competence) and subtests. A subtest consists of test tasks, which are the minimum constituent units of the test. The set of test tasks creates a test situation, which is presented by verbal (text) or non-verbal (drawing, diagram, table) means, and provides for a certain verbal or non-verbal reaction of the testees (answer, response). The reaction of the testees is understood as the expected response in verbal or non-verbal form (letters, numbers, etc.) of the multiple-choice or free response type. An important component of the test is also its specifications (test specifications), which establish the norms, conditions and instructions for its implementation and determine its purpose, type and appearance. The main specifications include the objectives of the test; the contingent of the testees; construct (theoretical basis of the test) being tested; number of test parts required to test certain knowledge, skills and abilities; time required to complete the test as a whole and each part in particular; methods and criteria for assessing the testees' answers; description of the possession of communicative competence according to levels; samples of test tasks and testees' answers. A separate test task also has such specifications as instructions for its completion, characteristics of the expected answer and the method of scoring.

The widespread use of linguodidactic tests in the control process is due to their undeniable advantages:

- saving classroom time due to the simultaneous testing of a large number of students and the compact written form of test tasks;
- ensuring the necessary completeness of testing coverage of knowledge and skills subject to control;
- cost-effectiveness of testing results due to the use of answer sheets and keys;
- simplicity of testing and determining the score for a person of average qualification;
- the possibility of using computer programs and technical devices;
- universality as the control covers all stages of the educational process.

The main disadvantages of linguodidactic tests are caused by the use of test tasks with selective answers:

- 1) guessing the correct answer from random and formal ones;
- 2) insufficient activity of thinking processes due to the presence of ready-made answers and a general orientation to the test result;
- 3) the possibility of involuntary memorization of incorrect answers;
- 4) the test situation may not be sufficiently informative and communicative due to the brevity of the context;
- 5) incorrect answer options may contain excessive information that distracts the testees and prevents them from determining the correct answer.

In this regard, the test expert must adhere to semantic balance among variants of the test task.

Let us consider the implementation of the communicative-activity model of control on the example of testing reading skills in English professionally oriented texts.

As is known, reading is a receptive type of speech activity that is directly related to thinking and understanding of what is read.

From the point of view of psycholinguistics, the mechanism of the reading process consists of three phases:

1) incentive-motivational: perception of information against the background of a positive emotional attitude towards reading and, thus, the presence of a motive for reading activity;

2) formative-formulatory or orientative-exploratory:

- the level of internal speech - predicting the content by headings, first words/sentences and creating a scheme (matrix) of what is predicted in the text;

- the level of internal speech - confirmation/refusal of the prediction regarding the content, the formation of syntagms and whole sentences from the text;

- understanding the text as a unity – integration of individual understandable sentences into a single whole, i.e. understanding the meaning of the text;

3) executive: performing a speech act (transmitting the content of the text, one's thoughts, feelings and impressions) based on an adequate understanding of the text.

Therefore, it is obvious that it is necessary to take into account the psychological mechanism of reading when developing the appropriate tests, since it determines both the functions of test tasks for controlling reading and the objects of control of the level of formation of speech competence in reading. Based on the structure of the reading mechanism, the following functions of test tasks for controlling reading can be distinguished:

1) creating motivation, which, together with the reader's emotional state, affects the depth of understanding of the text and the nature of the information to which the reader's attention is paid;

2) creating a subject of activity as performing one of the types of reading: introductory with an understanding of the main content of the text, studying with a full (detailed) understanding of the text, selective/reviewing in order to find the necessary information;

3) implementing activities based on text processing by performing the following operations in reading: quick review of the text; detailed reading to understand the main ideas and important details; using knowledge of linguistic skills: understanding grammatical categories, syntactic structures, lexical and/or grammatical units, vocabulary;

4) evaluating the results of activities in order to identify the reader's ability to understand texts on various topics.

Conclusions and further research prospects.

The implementation of the communicative-activity model of control is carried out by defining reading as a type of communicative activity, taking into account the psychological mechanisms of reading, which, in turn,

determine the objects of control and ensure the implementation of the functions of test tasks for reading control.

Prospects for further research can be aimed at developing an effective system for controlling the level of speech competence of future teacher-engineers in reading English-language professionally oriented texts. Assuming that it should be comprehensively based on a set of different control models, it is necessary to analyze the ways of implementing the systemic, competency-based and level-based model of control within the limits of this system. In addition, other factors need to be considered, including the purpose, objectives, and functions of such a system, the classification of tests and subtests according to their purpose of use and form, the qualities inherent in an effective control system, its specifics in non-language universities, ways to ensure the objectification of test tasks, etc.

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